

Flexible Electronics: What can it do? What should it do?

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Abstract—The development of low temperature, thin film transistor processes that has enabled flexible displays also presents opportunities for flexible electronics. A variety of flexible digital and analog electronics have been demonstrated, although typically of modest performance. We review the state-of-the-art in flexible electronics followed by a discussion of the constraints, remaining challenges and realistic potential applications of thin film transistors and flexible integrated systems.

Keywords- flexible electronics, thin film transistors

I. INTRODUCTION

Flexible electronics began with flexible solar cells which were silicon based but thinned down to improve their efficiency. Basically, flexible electronics deals with circuits developed using thin film transistors (TFT). The first TFTs were reported in 1968 by Brody and colleagues [1]. During the 1980s, the active matrix TFT backplanes were fabricated for display applications. This led to a huge success for the LCD industry. The amorphous silicon based backplanes were inexpensive to make and uniform across a large area.

Throughout the last four decades, there has been continuous improvement in developing TFTs on flexible substrates such as paper, polyimide, Mylar, stainless steel etc. Flexible solar cells have been extensively researched, and many of the manufacturing plants today develop amorphous silicon solar cells using roll-to-roll processes [2].

During the 1980s, the liquid-crystal display (LCD) industry began using amorphous silicon (a-Si:H) active matrix TFT backplanes for LCD displays. After an R&D effort of more than a decade, today we see flat panel displays being used in televisions, computer monitors, cellular phones, mp3 players

etc.

Fig. 1. Amorphous silicon backplane on Gen II PEN Substrate

Thin film transistor based circuits on flexible polyimide substrates were first demonstrated by Constant et al. in 1994 [3]. Since then several companies and research groups have demonstrated circuits and displays on flexible substrates using a-Si:H, organic materials, mixed oxide TFT and also hybrid organic/inorganic CMOS technologies [4-7]. The research effort is still ongoing to develop new materials and processes to manufacture flexible displays. Several electro-optic materials have been identified such as E-Ink Corp's electrophoretic ink, Kent Display's cholesteric material, organic light emitting diodes (OLED) etc. Fig. 1 shows an array of a-Si:H TFT backplanes for 1.1 inch diagonal flexible displays on heat stabilized polyethylene naphthalate (PEN) developed at Flexible Display Center at Arizona State University [8]. The size of the panel is 370 mm x 470 mm (Gen II). The panel is bonded to a glass carrier before it is processed in the Gen II pilot line. After the completion of the process, it is de-bonded from the carrier.

II. CURRENT STATUS OF THIN FILM ELECTRONICS

In this section, we will discuss the current trends in flexible electronics and the different TFT technologies available today to develop circuits and displays on large area substrates.

A. Amorphous Silicon Technology

Hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si:H) TFTs are the workhorse of today's active matrix LCD displays. Today, the LCD manufacturers are manufacturing panels on Gen 10 mother-glass which is 2880 mm x 3080 mm. These LCD panels are processed at higher temperatures which are not compatible with flexible substrates such as PEN, PET, etc. However, during the last decade, several research groups have shown progress in the development of flexible displays using a-Si:H TFT backplanes [4, 9, 10]. Fig. 2 shows a 4.1 inch active matrix OLED display on PEN using a-Si:H TFTs developed at the Flexible Display Center at ASU [11].

Fig. 2. A 4.1" QVGA OLED display on PEN

Materials and manufacturing processes for OLED displays are continuously evolving. The main driving force for OLED display is its emissive characteristics, good color saturation and clarity. It is also sunlight readable unlike many LCD technologies. The main limitation in using a-Si:H TFTs for OLED displays is the threshold voltage (V_t) shift of the TFTs. Due to electrical stress, the V_t of the TFTs increase over time which reduces the drive current of the TFTs. This will degrade the brightness of the OLEDs. Also, the lifetime of the OLED materials is limited due to moisture intake through the PEN substrate. Barrier coating is necessary to prevent this degradation.

Currently, there are a few ways of manufacturing flexible displays on plastic substrates – Surface Free Technology by Laser Annealing (SUFTLA), Electronics on Plastic by Laser Release (EPLaR), Bond-Debond method [12,13,4]. All these are low temperature processes which give rise to higher threshold voltage variations in a-Si:H TFTs. In order to reduce V_t shifts, the process temperature has to be increased and thus requires a substrate which can sustain higher temperatures. Princeton University researchers along with their industrial partners have shown high temperature plastics [14] which can be processed at 250 - 280 °C. Processing free standing PEN substrates is still a challenge as the size of the substrate

increases.

Another important area is the integration of drivers for flexible displays on the substrate. Although, there are multiple research groups and industrial partners working on flexible TFT backplanes, very few have shown functional integrated electronics on flexible substrates to drive these displays [15, 16]. Sarnoff worked on high temperature TFT process on glass substrates for a number of years and developed integrated row and column drivers for LCD displays. Several V_t compensation techniques were used in this design.

Row drivers are relatively easier to integrate using amorphous silicon technology. The V_t shift does not affect the row drivers as much as it does to the column drivers since the row drivers are “on” only for a small period of time in a frame. If the display is running at 60 Hz, then the frame time is 0.166 seconds and for a QVGA display, the row time is only 69 μ s. For column drivers, it is more important that the TFTs function with good stability since they are “on” throughout the frame time. Some of the work done on integrated drivers using low temperature amorphous silicon process on flexible substrates have been published by our group (FDC) in recent years [16, 17]. Fig 3 shows the circuit of a single column driver which can drive an electrophoretic display with 3 output levels. This circuit has been shown to be functional on stainless steel as well as PEN substrates. A 64x64 display with integrated column drivers was demonstrated as described in [17]. Due to its low mobility and high V_t shift, a-Si:H TFTs are not a good candidate for developing integrated source drivers for video rate displays. However, for bistable displays such as electrophoretic and cholesteric displays, a-Si:H TFT based integrated drivers can be used in applications which require only occasional image updates such as advertising, map applications, point of sale labels etc.

Fig. 3. Schematic of a single column of integrated source drivers for electrophoretic displays on PEN substrates.

B. Polysilicon Technology

Poly-Si TFTs are processed at higher temperature using laser re-crystallization of a-Si:H material and can have mobilities greater than 100 $\text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$. The threshold voltages of these TFTs are very stable and can be made in both varieties – n-type and p-type. Hence, Poly-Si TFTs can be used to develop display backplanes as well as CMOS digital circuits [18]. However, the process and substrate costs are

comparatively higher and hence restrict the use of these TFTs in higher end applications such as high resolution displays in smart phones and high-end radio frequency tags.

C. Organic Thin Film Transistors

Organic TFTs can be manufactured using a number of organic semiconductors such as Pentacene, TIPS Pentacene, etc. These semiconductors can be processed at low temperatures using solution processes or vacuum evaporated processes such as spin coating, and ink-jet printing. Roll-to-roll processing may bring down the cost of production. The Pentacene based TFTs are p-type with carrier mobilities ranging from 0.1 to $5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [19,20] which will allow them to be used in low speed applications such as active matrix electrophoretic displays. The OTFT is sensitive to air and hence its performance degrades over time when exposed to the environment. Barrier coating is required to protect it from exposure. Some of the research done at Stanford University shows that it is possible to develop mixed signal analog to digital converters using organic TFTs [21].

D. Single Crystal Silicon on Flexible Substrates

It is possible to develop single crystal silicon circuits on flexible substrates with mobilities greater than $500 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and response frequencies greater than 500 MHz [22, 23]. In this technique, a semiconducting micro/nanomaterial known as microstructured silicon ($\mu\text{-Si}$) is printed using dry transfer or solution based techniques onto plastic substrates to produce high performance TFTs [24].

E. Mixed Oxide Thin Film Transistors

Mixed oxide thin film transistors such as IZO, IGZO have been shown to provide better mobility, higher current densities and better stability compared to a-Si:H TFTs [25-27]. Another feature of mixed oxide TFTs is that they are transparent. Hence, there is much interest to develop transparent electronics on large area flexible substrates.

Fig. 4. V_t shift of low temperature IZO TFTs under DC bias stress

Simple digital inverters were built using low temperature (180°C) IZO TFTs and stressed electrically for more than 350 hours. Fig 4 shows the variation of V_t over time under positive DC stress for these TFTs and Fig 5 shows the stability of an inverter with an AC stress.

Fig. 5. Digital inverter using IZO TFTs stressed for 365 hours

F. Hybrid (CMOS) Technology

Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor technology has several advantages over nMOS only (a-Si:H, IZO, IGZO) or pMOS only (Pentacene) technologies. By including n-type TFTs and p-type TFTs on the same substrate, it is possible to implement CMOS circuits which reduce power consumption, leakage currents and improve the gain of the digital logic circuits. Some of the work done in this area is presented in [20, 21]. Research done at Flexible Display Center in collaboration with University of Texas at Dallas has shown that these CMOS logic circuits are more stable compared to a-Si:H TFT circuits. This is because the V_t of the a-Si:H shifts in positive direction with electrical stress while that of organic TFTs shift negative (Fig 6). In this technology, we have integrated a-Si:H TFTs and Pentacene TFTs on PEN substrate and successfully demonstrated a CMOS column driver for electrophoretic displays [28].

Fig. 6. V_t shift – a-Si:H nMOS and Pentacene pMOS

III. APPLICATIONS

Flexible electronic circuits can be used in several applications which require large area, rugged environments and have to be conformal to the device or structure. As discussed above, currently, the active matrix displays using flexible TFT backplanes is the most attractive application for industries since it does not require high speed devices comparable to single crystal silicon. For the future, however, it is important to have a vision with new applications which can only be done using flexible TFT based circuits. Some of the applications are discussed below.

A. Large Area Detectors

In the medical field, x-ray imaging is one of the most important tool to determine a patient's health. Digital x-ray imaging is gaining acceptance and has a long term economical advantage by having patients' records in digital format. By developing these x-ray imaging sensors on flexible substrates, it is possible to have portable equipments for field use such as in battlefield and for medical emergencies such as earthquakes, floods, etc. Potentially, a stretcher can have an integrated x-ray detector which sends the images wirelessly to the hospital servers for immediate use. This technology can be further expanded to detect neutrons, and gamma rays for security purposes in ports of entry and other public transport stations.

B. Prognostics and Diagnostics

Today, there are several autonomous machines which help in reconnaissance for the military and civilian applications. For prognostics and diagnostics, these machines have to be decommissioned temporarily and moved to a testing facility. This exercise is prohibitively expensive. Flexible electronics in the future can potentially be conformal to the surface of these vehicles/machines and the tests can be done onsite reducing the cost significantly. For example, flexible sensors can be put on the wings of an airplane to monitor structural health, air flow, etc.

C. Smart textiles

Recently, there is increase interest in smart textiles for health monitoring, entertainment and display applications. These "smart textiles" can be embedded with multiple sensors and display devices for monitoring heart rate, stress, monitoring toxic gases in the environment etc. Fig. 7 shows a concept of a smart textile with weave able "smart threads". Each "smart thread" is basically a shift register with a small display pixel and possibly a sensor, which can be used to transfer data from one end to the other. Data from all the "smart threads" can be read at the edge of the textile for further data processing.

D. Flexible Antennas

Transceivers are an important part of any wireless device. Future applications require some form of communication which requires high performance TFTs as well as integrated antennas. Researchers at ASU have shown flexible antennas fabricated on PEN substrate in the same fabrication line as the flexible displays [30].

Fig. 7. Smart textile concept

E. Blast sensors/dosimeters

In recent years, more and more soldiers are experiencing brain trauma due to exposure to a large number of blasts in the battlefield. In order to understand the effect of blasts on human brain, researchers are developing blast sensors/dosimeters which can measure the blast wave as well as the direction from which it came from [31].

F. Organic Photoreceptors

From past two decades, significant amount of research has been done on organic photoreceptors and organic imaging systems for xerography [32, 33]. However, much effort is needed to develop organic photoreceptors on flexible substrates and integrate on to roll drums.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper gives a brief overview of how the field of flexible electronics has evolved over the years and what the future holds for large area, flexible, rugged, low power electronics. Flexible displays have been the main focus so far for the industry. Several new manufacturing techniques are being developed from vacuum processing to ink-jet printing to roll-to-roll process. This paper introduces to the different TFT technologies being researched such as amorphous silicon, polysilicon, single crystal silicon, mixed oxide and organic TFTs. Some of the applications which can be developed on flexible substrates have been introduced.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Brody, T. Peter, "The thin film transistor - a late flowering bloom," *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 31, no.11, pp. 1614-1628, Nov 1984.
- [2] William S. Wong and Alberto Salleo, *Flexible electronics: materials and applications*, Springer Science and Business Media, 2009
- [3] A. Constant, S. G. Burns, H. R. Shanks, C. Gruber, A. Landin, D. Schmidt, C. Thielen, F. Olympie, T. Schumacher, and J. Cobbs, "Development of thin film transistor based circuits on flexible polyimide substrates," *Electrochemical Society Meeting*, 9-14 October 1994, Miami, Florida. Published Proceedings. Invited Paper
- [4] S.M. O'Rourke, D.E. Loy, C. Moyer, E.J. Bawolek, S.K. Ageno, B.P. O'Brien, M. Marrs, D. Bottesch, J. Dailey, R. Naujokaitis, J. P. Kaminski, D. R. Allee, S. M. Venugopal, J. Haq, N. Colaneri, G. B. Raupp, D.C. Morton and E.W. Forsythe, "Direct fabrication of a-Si:H thin film transistor arrays on plastic and metal foils for flexible displays," Proc. 26th Army Science Conference, Dec. 2008
- [5] M. G. Kane et al, "Analog and digital circuits using organic thin-film transistors on polyester substrates," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 21, no. 11, Nov 2000
- [6] Randy Hoffman, Tim Emery, Bao Yeh, Tim Koch, Warren Jackson, "Zinc Indium Oxide thin-film transistors for active-matrix display backplane," *Proc. of Society for Information Display*, 2009
- [7] S. Gowrisanker, M.A. Quevedo-Lopez, H. N. Alshareef, B. Gnade, S. Venugopal, R. Krishna, K. Kaftanoglu, D. Allee, "Low temperature integration of hybrid CMOS devices on plastic substrates," *Proc. Flexible Electronics and Displays Conference*, Phoenix, Arizona, Feb 2-5, 2009
- [8] Flexible Display Center, Arizona State University [online] <http://flexdisplay.asu.edu>
- [9] John K. Borchardt, "Developments in organic displays," *Materials Today*, Volume 7, Issue 9, September 2004, Pages 42-46, ISSN 1369-7021, DOI: 10.1016/S1369-7021(04)00401-8
- [10] S.E. Burns et. al, "Flexible active matrix displays," *Proc. Society for Information Display*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 19-21, 2005
- [11] D. E. Loy, Y. K. Lee, C. Bell, M. Richards, E. J. Bawolek, S. K. Ageno, C. Moyer, M. Marrs, S. M. Venugopal, J. P. Kaminski, N. Colaneri, S. M. O'Rourke, J. Silvermail, K. Rajan, R. Ma, M. Hack, and J. J. Brown, "Active matrix PHOLED displays on temporary bonded polyethylene naphthalate substrates with 180°C a-Si:H TFTs," *Proc. Society for Information Displays*, San Antonio, TX, May 31-June 5, 200
- [12] Sumio Utsunomiya, Satoshi Inoue, and Tatsuya Shimoda, "Low-temperature poly-Si TFT transferred onto plastic substrates by using surface free technology by laser ablation/annealing (SUFTLA)," *J. Soc. Inf. Display*, vol. 10, no.1, March 2002
- [13] Ian French, David George, Thierry Kretz, Francois Templier, and Herbert Lifka, "Flexible displays and electronics made in AM-LCD facilities by the EPLaR process," *SID Symposium Digest*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 1680-1683, May 2007
- [14] H. Bahman, K.H. Cherenack, A. Z. Kattamis, K. Long, S. Wagner, J.C Sturm, "Highly stable amorphous-silicon thin-film transistors on clear plastic," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 93, no.3, 2008
- [15] H. Lebrun, F. Maurice, J. Magarino, and N. Szydlo, "AMLCD with integrated drivers made with amorphous silicon TFTs," *Society for Information Display, Journal of*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 177-180, Dec 1995
- [16] S.M. Venugopal and D. R. Allee, "Integrated a-Si:H source drivers for 4" QVGA electrophoretic display on flexible stainless steel substrate," *IEEE Journal of Display Technology*, Vol. 3, No. 1, March 2007, pp. 57-63
- [17] Sameer M. Venugopal, Rahul Shringarpure, David R. Allee and Shawn M. O'Rourke, "Integrated a-Si:H Source Drivers for Electrophoretic Displays on Flexible Plastic Substrates", *Proc. 7th Annual Flexible Electronics & Displays Conference*, Phoenix, Arizona, pp. 1-5 Jan 2008
- [18] Po-Chin Kuo, Abbas Jamshidi-Roudbari, and Miltiadis Hatalis, "Electrical characteristics and mechanical limitation of polycrystalline silicon thin film transistor on steel foil under strain", *J. Appl. Phys.* vol. 106, no. 11, pp. 114502, Dec 2009
- [19] Dirk Zielke, Arved C. Hubler, Ulrich Hahn, Nicole Brandt, Matthias Bartzsch, Uta Fugmann, Thomas Fischer, Janos Veres, and Simon Ogier, "Polymer-based organic field-effect transistor using offset printed source/drain structures", *Appl. Phys. Lett.* vol. 87, pp.123508, 2005, DOI:10.1063/1.2056579
- [20] Manuel Quevedo, S. Gowrisanker, H.N. Alshareef, B. E. Gnade, D Allee, S Venugopal, R Krishna, and K Kaftanoglu, "Novel materials and integration schemes for CMOS-based circuits for flexible electronics," *Meet. Abstr. - Electrochem. Soc.* 902, 2408 (2009),
- [21] W. Xiong, U. Zschieschang, H. Klauk, and B. Murmann, "A 3V, 6b Successive Approximation ADC using Complementary Organic Thin-Film Transistors on Glass," to appear, *ISSCC Dig. Techn. Papers*, Feb. 2010
- [22] Jong-Hyun Ahn et. al., "High-speed mechanically flexible single-crystal silicon thin-film transistors on plastic substrates", *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 460-462, June 2006
- [23] Dae-Hyeong Kim et. al., "Ultrathin Silicon Circuits With Strain-Isolation Layers and Mesh Layouts for High-Performance Electronics on Fabric, Vinyl, Leather, and Paper," *Advanced Materials*, vol. 21, no. 36, pp. 3703-3707, Sept. 2009
- [24] E. Menard, K. J. Lee, D.-Y. Khang, R. G. Nuzzo, and J. A. Rogers, "A printable form of silicon for high performance thin film transistors on plastic substrates", *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol.84, no. 26, pp. 5398-5400, June 2004, DOI:10.1063/1.1767591
- [25] P. G'ormn, M. Sander, J. Meyer, M. Kr'ogger, E. Becker, H.-H. Johannes, and W. K. T. Riedl, "Towards see-through displays: Fully transparent thin-film transistors driving transparent organic light-emitting diodes," *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 18, pp. 738-41, 2006.
- [26] U. Ozgur, Ya. I. Alivov, C. Liu, A. Teke, M. A. Reshchikov, S. Dogan, V. Avrutin, S.-J. Cho, and H. Morkoc, "A comprehensive review of ZnO materials and devices," *J. Appl. Phys.* Vol. 98, pp. 041301, 2005.
- [27] Sameer M. Venugopal, Edward Bawolek, Michael Marrs, Korhan Kaftanoglu, Aritra Dey, James R. Wilson, Anil Indluru, Terry L. Alford, David R. Allee and Shawn O'Rourke, "Effect of bias stress on Indium Zinc Oxide thin film transistors manufactured at low temperature", *Proc. 9th annual Flexible Electronics and Display Conference*, Phoenix, AZ, Feb 2010
- [28] D. R. Allee, S. Venugopal, R. Krishna, K. Kaftanoglu, M. Quevedo-Lopez, S. Gowrisanker, A. Avendano-Bolivar, and B. Gnade, "Flexible CMOS and electrophoretic displays," invited paper, *Society for Information Displays*, International Symposium, Digest of Technical Papers, San Antonio, TX, May 31-June 5, 2009
- [29] [online] <http://www.warwickaudiotech.com/index.php>
- [30] B. Gnade, M. Quevedo, D. Allee, S. Venugopal, C. Balanis, T. Jackson, H. McHugh, K. Baugh, E. Forsythe, and D. Morton, "Flexible integrated sensor systems," invited paper, *Special Operations Forces Industry Conference*, Tampa, FL, June 2-4, 200
- [31] Daniel J, Garner S, Nga N T, Knights J, Arias A. C, "Sensing blast events with flexible sensor tapes", *Proc. 9th annual Flexible Electronics and Displays Conference*, Phoenix, AZ, Feb 2010.
- [32] Borsenberger P.M, Weiss D.S, Organic Photoreceptors for imaging systems, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1993
- [33] Borsenberger P.M, Weiss D.S, Organic Photoreceptors for Xerography, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1998

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